

Mammal
SOCIETY

National Harvest Mouse Survey

Results from fourth survey

2024 - 2025

The Mammal Society's National Harvest Mouse Survey

Results from the Fourth Survey, 2024-2025

Photo by Phil Orris

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About the Mammal Society

Established in 1954, the Mammal Society strives for a future in which sustainable mammal populations thrive as part of healthy and diverse ecosystems benefiting people and nature across the British Isles and Ireland.

- We work to ensure a bright future for mammals in the British Isles by inspiring, informing, supporting and enhancing conservation projects and policies that protect and restore native mammal populations and their habitats
- We empower conservationists, students, citizen scientists and nature champions to play a key role in mammal conservation now and in the future through providing training, resources and survey activations
- We seek to build public awareness of and support for mammal conservation through education, communications and campaigns

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Executive Summary

The 2024–2025 season marked the fourth year of the National Harvest Mouse Survey. During this period, volunteers, regional coordinators, and wildlife organisations conducted structured and ad-hoc surveys across the UK to record harvest mouse (*Micromys minutus*) nest presence and associated habitat data. In addition to standard field efforts, this year introduced a methodological addition: species distribution modelling (SDM) using MaxEnt. This approach enabled the identification of environmental conditions favouring harvest mouse presence and predicted potentially suitable, but under-surveyed, areas.

Key findings included a marked reduction in the number of structured surveys compared to previous years, consistent with longer-term patterns linked to volunteer retention challenges and site accessibility issues, such as regional flooding. Despite reduced effort, novel insights emerged from SDM analyses. Climate variables such as annual mean temperature, precipitation seasonality, and temperature extremes emerged as influential predictors of habitat suitability.

The SDM outputs not only highlight ecologically important variables but also assist in guiding future survey prioritisation. Regions predicted to be suitable but currently lacking records are now identifiable, making future monitoring more targeted and efficient. These outputs contribute directly to the Mammal Society's goal of expanding ecological knowledge and improving conservation strategies for small mammals in the UK.

The continuation of coordinated surveys combined with predictive modelling represents a promising framework for future assessments of this species and others that are challenging to monitor using traditional means alone.

Introduction

Background

The harvest mouse (*Micromys minutus*) is Britain's smallest rodent and the only native species with a prehensile tail adapted for climbing. Due to its elusive nature, small size, and patchy distribution, it has historically been under-recorded across much of its range. Although not currently classified as a species of conservation concern at the national level, the harvest mouse remains vulnerable to habitat loss, changes in agricultural practices, and fragmentation of key vegetation types such as tall grasses, reedbeds, and marginal scrub.

Recognising the need for a comprehensive, standardised effort to map its distribution, the Mammal Society launched the National Harvest Mouse Survey in 2021. The survey aims to collate presence data from across the UK, improve understanding of habitat associations, and identify key strongholds or data gaps in current knowledge. The project also contributes toward broader goals of engaging the public in wildlife monitoring and building a long-term dataset suitable for conservation analysis.

Surveys are primarily conducted through visual nest searches, carried out by volunteers and coordinated by regional leads and local wildlife groups. Nests are used as a proxy for presence, as harvest mice are rarely seen directly. In previous survey years, nest records have been compiled into national distribution maps, and descriptive analyses of habitat context and regional coverage have been produced.

For the 2024–2025 survey year, the project introduced a new analytical layer: the use of species distribution modelling (SDM) to predict areas of likely habitat suitability based on observed nest records and environmental variables. This modelling approach enhances the interpretation of existing data, reveals unsurveyed areas of high potential, and provides an additional tool to assist with prioritising future survey efforts. In doing so, the survey continues to align with the Mammal Society’s mission to improve scientific understanding of the UK’s mammal fauna and to support evidence-based conservation planning.

Key Findings

- A significant decrease in structured survey submissions was observed during the 2024–2025 season, continuing a trend seen in previous years. Contributing factors included reduced volunteer retention and adverse environmental conditions in key regions.
- Presence-only and structured survey data recorded numerous nest sightings, with metadata capturing nest dimensions, associated plant species, and habitat context.
- The SDM analysis using MaxEnt revealed that annual mean temperature, temperature seasonality, and precipitation patterns were the strongest predictors of habitat suitability.
- The SDM identified several climatically suitable regions where no current records exist, offering new targets for future survey efforts.

Considerations for the Future

Looking ahead, several important considerations have emerged to refine both the scientific robustness and conservation impact of the National Harvest Mouse Survey. Species distribution modelling (SDM) has proven to be a valuable addition, offering predictive insights that complement field-based records. To maximise its utility, future survey campaigns should aim to reduce spatial and effort-related biases that arise from overreliance on structured, pre-determined transects. While structured surveys remain vital for collecting standardised data, a more balanced approach that incorporates randomised site selection could diversify habitat coverage and improve the ecological insights of SDM outputs.

Another key improvement area is data completeness. Surveyors should be strongly encouraged to use the standardised data collection formats. Importantly, non-detection data — instances where no nests or live animals are found — should not be overlooked. These records are essential for mapping survey effort and for developing bias layers used in model calibration. Real non-presence data is arguably more realistic than Maxent’s pseudo-absences and its use should take precedent when possible.

Finally, continued investment in training, volunteer retention, and feedback mechanisms will ensure data quality and consistency. As surveys continue year-on-year, the project will be well-positioned to track long-term ecological trends and contribute substantively to national conservation planning. The integration of SDMs, combined with a maturing field dataset, offers a scalable, repeatable model for monitoring elusive or under-recorded species across fragmented landscapes. To maintain or improve the robustness of and insights provided by the SDMs and statistical analyses, a stronger emphasis on volunteer engagement is strongly advised.

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Glossary of Terms

2021-22 Survey – The term used to describe the results and data from the first survey year conducted between the beginning of October 2021 and the end of March 2022.

2022-23 Survey – The term used to describe the results and data from the second survey year conducted between the beginning of October 2022 and the end of March 2023.

2023-24 Survey – The term used to describe the results and data from the third survey year conducted between the beginning of October 2023 and the end of March 2024.

Survey – A record with location, harvest mouse nest numbers and information on effort, specifically duration spent looking for harvest mice and number of people searching.

Survey effort – In the terms of this survey effort or survey effort is recorded as people hours or the multiplication of the number of people and the duration that they spent search for harvest mouse nests during a survey.

Presence-only – A record of harvest mouse presence or absence that does not include any information on survey effort.

Hectad – A 10 by 10 km British Ordnance Survey National Grid square presented using the British National Grid projection system (ESPG: 27700).

Methods

The 2024–2025 harvest mouse survey season ran from October 2024 through March 2025, coinciding with the period of maximum nest detectability due to reduced vegetation cover. Surveys were primarily conducted by trained volunteers and regional coordinators affiliated with local mammal groups, wildlife organisations, or independent citizen scientists.

Participants were instructed to search for harvest mouse nests within suitable habitats, including grassland, hedgerows, reedbeds, and farmland margins. Nests were recorded when found both during structured searches and opportunistically, in line with guidelines provided by the Mammal Society. The core protocol required surveyors to systematically search a 50 m transect within a habitat patch, estimating the time spent, distance covered, and number of people involved.

To ensure standardisation across surveyors and sites, resources such as illustrated guides, online briefings, and exemplar data sheets were provided at the beginning of the survey window. Participants were encouraged to follow the structured protocol where possible, though ad-hoc nest reports were also accepted to enhance spatial coverage.

Data Collection

Data were submitted through multiple channels: the Mammal Mapper app, standardised spreadsheets, and email-based submission forms. For each nest encountered, surveyors were asked to provide information including:

- GPS coordinates, grid references or whatthreewords.
- Number of nests found.
- Nest height and diameter.
- Time spent searching.
- Habitat context (e.g., grassland type, field margin, scrub edge).
- Survey effort (survey start time, end time, duration, number of people).

Records were separated into structured surveys and ad-hoc observations.

To maintain data quality and spatial consistency, all location information was cross-checked for plausibility against national boundaries, land cover maps, and administrative units. Duplicate reports were merged by comparing location, time, and nest characteristics. Structured surveys were prioritized for analysis.

SDM Data and Methods

To estimate habitat suitability for the harvest mouse (*Micromys minutus*) across the UK, species distribution modelling (SDM) was conducted using MaxEnt version 3.4.4 (Phillips et al., 2006). MaxEnt is a presence-background algorithm that estimates the most uniform (i.e., maximum entropy) probability distribution constrained by environmental conditions at presence locations. It has been widely validated for ecological niche modelling and has shown strong predictive performance in studies involving limited and spatially biased datasets (Elith et al., 2011).

MaxEnt was chosen for its efficacy with presence-only data, its capacity to incorporate complex interactions between variables through nonlinear features, and its interpretability through tools such as response curves, jackknife analyses, and variable contribution metrics. Compared to other presence-only algorithms (e.g., GARP or envelope-based models), MaxEnt has demonstrated superior accuracy and robustness in independent benchmarks (Elith et al., 2006; Phillips et al., 2017).

Bias Correction & Validation Strategy

Sampling bias is a known issue in citizen science and volunteer-based ecological surveys, where survey effort tends to cluster around accessible, familiar, or ecologically appealing areas (Fourcade et al., 2014; Kramer-Schadt et al., 2013). To mitigate this spatial bias, spatial thinning was applied using the spThin package in R (Aiello-Lammens et al., 2015). This ensured a minimum distance between records, reducing spatial autocorrelation while preserving ecological signal. The thinned dataset included 830 presence points for training and 414 for testing.

Crossvalidation, which partitions data into k folds was the chosen method of replication for the model. Each fold served once as the test dataset while the remaining two-thirds were used for training. Crossvalidation improves robustness by accounting for variability due to random partitioning (Fielding & Bell, 1997), reduces the risk of overfitting to spatial clusters, and offers better generalisation than subset testing (Radosavljevic & Anderson, 2014).

Three replicates were used to capture uncertainty and ensure stability across partitions. Multiple replicate runs are strongly recommended in SDM workflows to assess model consistency and guard against random artefacts in data splits (Warren et al., 2020; Morales et al., 2017).

Environmental Variables

Environmental predictors included 20 continuous variables: 19 bioclimatic variables and elevation, sourced from the Bioclim dataset, widely used in ecological modelling for its global coverage and relevance to species' physiological constraints (Booth et al., 2014).

For ease of interpretation, Table 1 describes each coded variable name.

Table 1 - Descriptions of each bioclim variable

Variable	Units
BIO1 = Annual Mean Temperature	C*100
BIO2 = Mean Diurnal Range (Mean of monthly (max temp - min temp))	C*100
BIO3 = Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (×100)	
BIO4 = Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation ×100)	C
BIO5 = Max Temperature of Warmest Month	C*100
BIO6 = Min Temperature of Coldest Month	C*100
BIO7 = Temperature Annual Range (BIO5-BIO6)	C*100
BIO8 = Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	C*100
BIO9 = Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	C*100
BIO10 = Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	C*100
BIO11 = Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	C*100
BIO12 = Annual Precipitation	mm
BIO13 = Precipitation of Wettest Month	mm
BIO14 = Precipitation of Driest Month	mm
BIO15 = Precipitation Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation)	mm
BIO16 = Precipitation of Wettest Quarter	mm
BIO17 = Precipitation of Driest Quarter	mm
BIO18 = Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	mm
BIO19 = Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	mm
BIO20 = Elevation	km

All layers were projected to a common coordinate system, resampled to uniform resolution, and clipped to a national UK shapefile.

MaxEnt Settings and Tuning

Model settings were configured as follows:

- Feature classes: hinge, linear, product, and quadratic (auto-selected)
- Maximum iterations: 5000 (to ensure convergence)
- Output format: cloglog (for easier interpretation of probability values)
- Threshold rule: 10 percentile training presence
- Background points: 10,404 (default sample from study area extent)

Jackknife tests and response curves were generated to assess the relative influence and behaviour of each predictor. The cloglog output scale was chosen because it closely approximates true presence probabilities and is more interpretable than raw or logistic outputs (Phillips et al., 2017).

To avoid overfitting and reduce redundancy, environmental variables were assessed across three modelling rounds. In each round, variables were evaluated using:

- Percent contribution to training gain
- Permutation importance based on test AUC drops

- Jackknife tests evaluating gain and AUC when each variable was omitted or used in isolation

Variables contributing <1% in the last replicates were excluded in subsequent rounds. This iterative pruning allowed simplification without sacrificing predictive power (Zhang et al., 2019) by removing redundant information or non-important variables without missing out on insights.

Comparison with Correlation-Filtered Variable Model

To test an alternative approach, a separate MaxEnt model was run using a reduced variable set. Here, Pearson correlation matrices were computed across predictors, and from each cluster of highly correlated variables ($|r| > 0.7$), one or two were retained to reduce multicollinearity (Dormann et al., 2013). This model performed less effectively, excluding several informative variables such as bioclim_7 and bioclim_10. While simpler, it underrepresented important climatic gradients and created a habitat suitability map that, according to current knowledge appeared too permissive.

Given its superior predictive power and alignment with known ecological drivers, the crossvalidated iterative model was selected as the final version for analysis.

Results

Table 1 - Basic nest and presence-only related statistics across the past three survey years

	2 nd year	3rd year	4rd year
Number of surveys	843	435	298
Number of nests from surveys	1593	1178	542
Nests with details info	972 (61%)	726 (62%)	369 (68%)
Presence only records	377	387	768
Total nests	2091	1618	1310

Nest Numbers

During the fourth survey year (October 2024 to March 2025), 298 surveys were conducted, down from 435 in the third year and 843 in the second year. This continued reduction in participation may reflect a combination of factors, including challenging weather conditions, reduced promotional outreach, and possible surveyor fatigue, as discussed below.

A total of 1,310 nests were recorded, compared to 1,618 in the third year and 2,091 in the second year (Table 1). Of these, 542 came from structured surveys, with the remainder recorded as presence-only submissions. Notably, 369 nests (68%) from surveys included detailed information on their positions, nest heights, diameters, and the plant species or habitat in which they were found. This represents a slight increase

in the proportion of detailed records compared to the third year (62%) and the second year (61%).

Presence-only records increased substantially in the fourth year, rising to 768 compared to 387 in the third year and 377 in the second year. These records document nests without associated survey effort data and now make up a significantly larger proportion of the total dataset than in previous years.

Survey effort

Survey effort in the fourth year was spread across the UK and split between 220 template recording form submissions and 78 Mammal Mapper app submissions. Combined, these surveys covered 113 unique sites, with template surveys accounting for 76 sites and Mammal Mapper for 37 sites. In total, 71 individual observers contributed.

The total survey time amounted to around 222 hours, with template-based surveys contributing the majority (about 142 hours) and Mammal Mapper surveys adding approximately 80 hours. Average transect duration was just over 52 minutes for template surveys and almost 62 minutes for Mammal Mapper surveys.

Geographical coverage

In 2024–2025, surveys covered 88 hectads (3.04% of all hectads in Great Britain) and 125 tetrads (0.20% of all tetrads), a reduction from the 195 hectads and 318 tetrads covered in the third year. Of these, 21 hectads and 32 tetrads represented non-detection surveys, with the remainder recording harvest mouse presence.

When data from all four survey years are combined, the NHMS has provided records from 480 hectads (16.57% of all hectads) and 1,057 tetrads (1.71% of all tetrads).

Across these surveyed hectads, harvest mice were recorded in 351 (73.13%), while 129 (26.87%) showed no detections. Figures illustrating the presence and non-detection of harvest mice across hectads and tetrads, both for the fourth year and combined across all years, provide a visual representation of these trends (Figure 1, Figure 2).

Figure 1 - Presence status of surveyed hectads and ad-hoc records in the 2024-2025 season

Figure 2 - Presence status of harvest mice in surveyed hectads and ad-hoc records across all survey years

Repeated surveys

Of the hectads surveyed across all four years, 16 were consistently monitored, with 167 surveys conducted in these areas. Ten hectads showed consistent nest presence in every survey year, suggesting broad-scale persistence of harvest mouse populations. However, survey locations within each hectad may have varied by up to 14.14 km (the diagonal distance of a hectad) between years, limiting our ability to confirm true population stability at finer scales. Seven hectads exhibited intermittent presence, with nests detected in one or more, but not all, years, indicating potential local fluctuations or variation in survey effort. Notably, four hectads (SX29, TQ77, TR15, TR16) that had shown presence in at least one of the first three years recorded no presence in Year 4, which may reflect genuine local declines or simply differences in survey coverage. In the case of tetrads, four were surveyed in all four years, with 29 surveys conducted. Two of these tetrads showed consistent nest presence (including SW97P at Lundy Bay), while two displayed intermittent presence. One tetrad (TR15U) lost presence in Year 4 despite detections in earlier years (Table 2).

Table 3 - Presence (P) and Non Detection (NP) in consistently surveyed hectad and tetrads over the past 4 surveys

Hectad	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
SS50	P	P	P	P
SW95	P	P	P	P
SW96	P	P	P	P
SW97	P	P	P	P
SX17	P	P	P	P
SX37	P	P	P	P
SX49	P	P	P	P
SX76	P	P	P	P
SY18	P	P	P	P
TQ44	P	P	P	P
SX29	ND	ND	P	ND
TQ77	P	P	P	ND
TR15	P	P	P	ND
SS43	ND	P	P	P
SY08	P	P	ND	P
TR16	P	P	P	ND
Tetrad	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
SW97P	P	P	P	P
SX49D	P	P	P	P
TR15U	P	P	P	ND
SS43K	ND	P	P	P

SDM Results

The final SDM, derived from the second round of crossvalidation using spatially thinned presence records, yielded a mean AUC of $0.83.5 \pm 0.007$, indicating strong discriminatory ability between presence and background points. Regularized training gain was 0.843, and test gain was 0.811, supporting the model's predictive reliability. The ROC curve showed high sensitivity and specificity, and omission rates at the 10-percentile training presence threshold remained acceptably low (<9%). The predicted habitat suitability map can be seen below (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Predicted habitat suitability for harvest mice across the UK using the cloglog transformation. Warmer colours indicate higher suitability.

The MaxEnt output included both percent contribution and permutation importance metrics for each environmental variable. While percent contribution reflects the heuristic path the algorithm took during model fitting, permutation importance quantifies how much each variable uniquely contributes to model performance by measuring the drop in AUC when the variable's values are randomly permuted (Phillips et al., 2006; Elith et al., 2011). Discrepancies between these two metrics are common, especially when collinearity is present (Dormann et al., 2013); as bioclim variables are derived from the same data, such collinearity was expected. The percent contribution and permutation importance values of each variable in the final model can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4 - Variable contributions indicate the most important predictors in building the model and those with unique information. Highlighted variables show particularly strong values in one of the two columns.

Variable	Percent contribution	Permutation importance
bioclim_1	28.2	0.2
bioclim_2	27.3	1
bioclim_3	11.9	11.6
bioclim_10	6.7	12.4
bioclim_17	3.9	1.7
bioclim_11	3.7	13.2
bioclim_19	3.2	1.1
bioclim_18	3.1	1.4
bioclim_14	2.2	9.7
bioclim_20	1.9	3.5
bioclim_8	1.7	0
bioclim_9	1.3	7.8
bioclim_7	1.3	11.4
bioclim_13	1.1	1.4
bioclim_15	1	14.9
bioclim_6	0.8	2.7

In this model, BIO1 (Annual Mean Temperature) contributed the most to the training process (28.2%), followed closely by BIO2 (Mean Diurnal Range) at 27.3%. However, their permutation importance values were negligible (0.2% and 1%, respectively), suggesting they provided redundant information contained in other variables despite having been used extensively to build the model. This is likely due to multicollinearity, a known challenge in ecological modelling (Graham 2003; Cade 2015) and highlights the importance of interpreting percent contribution cautiously.

Conversely, BIO15 (Precipitation Seasonality) had a minimal contribution score (1%) but the highest permutation importance (14.9%). This implies that it contains unique environmental information not found in other variables. Similar patterns exist in BIO11 (Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter) and BIO10 (Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter), both of which had modest percent contributions (3.7% and 6.7%, respectively) but high permutation importance values (13.2% and 12.4%).

Variables like BIO3 (Isothermality) and BIO7 (Temperature Annual Range) scored consistently high in both metrics, which indicates robust and reliable predictors.

In contrast, BIO8 (Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter) and BIO6 (Minimum Temperature of Coldest Month) scored poorly in both tables, suggesting that they offered little to model performance.

Understanding how predictors affected model gain was done by analysing the response curves (Figure 4, variables previously highlighted only).

Figure 4 - Response curves of the seven most influential variables

The response curve for BIO1 (Annual Mean Temperature, top left) exhibited a narrow peak in predicted suitability between approximately 10.0°C and 10.5°C, after which there's a sharp drop, which suggests low suitability, and a flat line at the end which represents a lack of signal. This suggests the model associates harvest mouse presence with mild temperatures overall but derives little additional predictive value from this variable, as evidenced by its very low permutation importance (0.2%, Table 1).

The response curve for BIO2 (Mean Diurnal Range, lower left corner) displays a sharp peak around 15.7°C and 16.6°C, where predicted suitability increased steeply before declining. Outside of this range, the model's prediction remained neutral. This lone peak combined with no signal on either side may reflect a statistical artefact created by a set of conditions commonly found in highly recorded areas. While BIO2 contributed significantly during model training (27.3%), its low permutation importance (1%) indicates that it does not provide substantial unique information and is, as expected, correlated with other temperature variables in the model.

There was a strong positive relationship between BIO3 (Isothermality) and model gain, peaking between values of approximately 6 and 8 and plateauing after.

BIO3 demonstrated both high percent contribution (11.9%) and high permutation importance (11.6%), indicating it was relevant to model building and contributed unique information.

With BIO7 (Temperature Annual Range) there was a consistent increase in predicted suitability between approximately 10°C and 18°C, followed by a plateau. This trajectory indicates that suitability increases with broader annual temperature variations. With a low percent contribution (1.3%) and high permutation importance (11.4%), while it wasn't used extensively to build the model, the information it provided was unique.

The response curve for BIO10 displays strong inverse relationship, evidenced by a steep decline in predicted suitability starting at around 13°C, with signal being lost at approximately 52°C. Despite a moderate percent contribution of 6.7%, the higher permutation importance at 12.4% suggests BIO10 provided information that did not overlap with that of other predictors.

The response curve for BIO11 (Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter) revealed a steep rise in suitability between 11.0°C and 15.0°C, with a peak in model prediction at the upper end of this range. Suitability declined beyond 15°C and plateaued after. Despite a modest percent contribution (3.7%), BIO11 had high permutation importance (13.2%), which marked it as another predictor with unique information.

Lastly, BIO15 (Precipitation Seasonality) displayed a gradual rise in predicted suitability with increasing variability in rainfall, peaking around a coefficient of variation of 21.7%. Beyond this threshold, suitability dropped sharply. Despite a low percent contribution during model training (1.0%), BIO15 had the highest permutation importance (14.9%), underscoring its role as a uniquely informative variable.

Discussion

This report aimed to obtain initial insights into harvest mouse ecology in the UK with species distribution modelling to help refine harvest mouse surveys by the Mammal Society as well as potentially inform feedback for the volunteers that continue showing support for this cause.

The model identified several variables as important components of harvest mouse habitat suitability, which included temperature metrics both seasonally and annually, as well as precipitation seasonality. Among the predictors, two temperature-related variables stood out: BIO1 (Annual Mean Temperature) and BIO2 (Mean Diurnal Range) had the highest percent contributions but did not contain unique information, as was reflected in their low permutation contributions. Habitat suitability peaked between approximately 10.0°C and 10.5°C (BIO1); temperatures outside this range may impact vegetation used for nesting or disturb foraging. Further, the predicted peak in suitability regarding the mean diurnal range appears to indicate some sensitivity to fluctuations in temperature.

However, the low permutation importance for both variables indicate the information they carry is not unique to them and can be explained, and possibly affected, by other variables. In future, one or the other could be removed to mitigate against multicollinearity without losing information.

The idea that thermal stability is important to harvest mice is brought up a gain by BIO3 (Isothermality), which represents the ratio of diurnal to annual variation in temperature and scored highly on both percentage and permutation importance. The positive relationship between BIO3 and habitat suitability suggests a preference for habitats that buffer daily and seasonal thermal extremes, such as hedgerows and areas with dense vegetation, which aligns with current literature (Bence et al. 2003; Occhiuto et al. 2021). BIO11 (Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter) supports the notion that *H. minutus* requires milder winters as well, possibly due to their high metabolic rate and small size making thermoregulation more difficult (Peralta-Maraver and Rezende 2020; Hu et al. 2024). Similarly, higher mean temperatures of the highest quarter (BIO10) reduced habitat suitability, as expected for such a small mammal's thermoregulatory capacity.

Precipitation seasonality (BIO15) presented interesting results: apparently a highly informative variable, evidenced by high permutation importance, but negligible overall importance. Suitability peaked with moderate rainfall variation and declined with high variation, suggesting that the harvest mouse could be vulnerable to flooding or drying. Such events could reduce invertebrate prey density (Adis and Junk 2002; McMullen and Lytle 2012; Batzer et al. 2016) or alter vegetation structure (Liu et al. 2023; Qian et al. 2023).

Despite the information derived from climatic variables, the model does not account for habitat type, which creates an important gap to fill. Predictors related to land use and vegetation type would improve the results' robustness and further point the Mammal Society's efforts to gain a fuller understanding of the *H. minutus* ecology. Such variables should be in raster format and set to a resolution that matches the species scale - too coarse a resolution would cause models to miss finer-scale relationships,

but higher resolutions would be resource intensive to obtain. Despite this limitation, the model suggested several areas as suitable (Figure 1) that are currently undersampled according to existing survey records. Areas in Lincolnshire, parts of Nottinghamshire and Cambridgeshire had high suitability, but few tetrads recorded. A similar pattern is present in parts of West Somerset and North Devon, where there is little surveyor activity. In North Wales and Anglesey there is moderate predicted habitat suitability but low presence records. Areas near the border and central band of Scotland also show some habitat suitability where survey effort is low.

Notably, the model predicts moderate suitability in parts of Northern Ireland despite there being no presence records there for the model to train with. This suggests both possible suitable habitat for the harvest mouse and that the model can generalize to areas beyond where it has training data. These findings suggest there to be several areas throughout the UK that could benefit from harvest mouse surveys to improve their habitat preference and population ecology better.

It is also important to consider the impact of spatial and recorder effort bias on the model's predictions, which is particularly visible in South Wales and along the Welsh coastline. These areas show high predicted suitability, but their geographic context and dense concentration of presence records over several survey years suggest the model may be responding to repeated survey effort rather than genuine habitat patterns. This illustrates how structured, but non-random survey designs can inadvertently skew species distribution models. To reduce this bias and improve model robustness, future efforts should combine expert knowledge with more randomized survey locations. Methods to mitigate spatial and effort bias include bias files and spatial thinning (Steen et al. 2021), the latter of which was used for the present model. Ultimately, however, randomized survey strategies are required to substantially reduce the noise in presence data without removing valuable information.

Another vital part of species distribution modelling is to balance avoiding overfitting, which occurs when a model "fits" so well to its training data that it is unable to predict occurrence outside those areas, and making the model more complex in a manner that reflects reality. This balance must be considered when choosing to add more predictors, such as the presence of harvest mouse predators. Theoretically, introducing predator-related predictors could reveal interactions relevant to harvest mouse habitat suitability. They would also add further noise to the data however, and as such thorough testing is advised before the reliance on any model. Statistical testing for multicollinearity allows for a selection of variables from clusters of related variables, while iterative removal of variables allows for independent models to run absent redundant predictors. Throughout testing, visual inspection of suitability maps for highly unlikely results and the tracking of AUC values are required to ensure not too many variables have been removed. To ensure statistical robustness and ecological realism, future models should be employed with these considerations in mind.

On the modelling process itself, these findings reinforce the value of multi-metric evaluation in variable selection. While percent contribution guides us toward variables that the model relied upon, permutation importance highlights those with unique, irreplaceable predictive value. Thoughtful modelling, combined with expert knowledge, can therefore lay the groundwork for evidence-based insight into harvest mouse

ecology and potential vulnerabilities. This is particularly important for informed conservation planning, particularly when dealing with increasing urbanization (Birnie-Gauvin et al. 2016) and climate change (Levinsky et al. 2007). This report argues that species distribution modelling can be a useful tool to improve the Mammal Society's Annual Harvest Mouse Survey, provide feedback to volunteers and inform future conservation planning.

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